

LOCAL BUCKLING OF COMPOSITE FRP SHAPES

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SUMMARY: Local buckling analyses of fiber reinforced plastic beams and columns require numerical procedures. In this paper simple (explicit) approximate formulas are derived which enable the designer to determine the local buckling loads of axially loaded and bent beams and columns. Numerical examples are also presented for box- I-, C-, and L sections, and good agreement was found between the derived expressions, the finite element calculations, the analytical results, and the experimental buckling loads.

KEYWORDS: local buckling, columns, flange buckling, web buckling, FRP

INTRODUCTION

Local buckling analysis is a major consideration in the design of thin-walled FRP sections. Local buckling analyses of members can be performed by modeling the wall segments as orthotropic plates and by assuming that edges common to two or more plates remain straight. Then the buckling load is determined either (i) „exactly” (assuming that all the wall segments buckle simultaneously and the continuity conditions at the plate intersections are satisfied) or (ii) approximately, by considering the wall segments as individual plates, which are elastically restrained by the adjacent walls [5].

Using the first method, analyses (which require numerical solutions) were developed for determining the local buckling loads of members consisting of orthotropic wall segments subjected to axial loads [11] and bending [22]. When the second method is used (e.g., only one of the wall segments is considered, which is elastically restrained by the adjacent walls) the two keys to the solution are (a) to determine the elastic restraints caused by the adjacent walls (see [14], [2], [18]), and (b) to calculate the buckling load of the plate whose edges are restrained.

The buckling analyses of long orthotropic plates with different edge conditions were treated by several authors; however closed form expressions were available only for a few cases ([3], [12] and [19]), such as axially loaded plates with two simply supported edges, or plates with one simply supported edge and one free edge. Recently, explicit expressions were published for the calculation of the buckling loads of plates when the edges are rotationally restrained, which are summarized in the next section.

Fig. 1: Local buckling of the top flange of a box section beam

The goal of this paper is to use these results and to develop simple explicit expressions for calculating the local buckling loads of thin-walled FRP composite beams and columns. In [8] we already developed expressions for the local buckling of axially loaded *box-beams*, and for the flange buckling of axially loaded *I-beams*. In this paper these results are generalized for the local buckling analysis of thin-walled (box-, I-, C-, Z-, and L-) members, subjected to axial load and bending.

We consider open and closed thin-walled section prismatic members consisting of flat rectangular wall segments. The layup of each wall segment is orthotropic and symmetrical with respect to its midplane. The material and the layup may be different in each wall segment, but must be uniform along the width of each wall segment of the member. Axial compressive stresses, introduced by axial force and bending moment may cause local buckling in thin-walled members. We determine the load on the member which results in local buckling. We assume that the material behaves in a linearly elastic manner and the deformations are small.

BUCKLING OF UNIDIRECTIONALLY LOADED LONG PLATES

We consider plates with length L_x and width L_y ($L_x \gg L_y$) subjected to uniformly distributed and linearly varying axial force N_x . The layup of the plate is orthotropic and symmetrical. Expressions of the buckling loads for important practical cases are summarized in Table 1. Solutions of the cases shown in the first, third, and in the last rows are given by Lekhnitskii [12], the expression of the fifth row is reported by Barbero [3], and the other expressions were derived recently; the numbers in the square brackets refer to the appropriate articles.

In this Table there are two different ways as the long edges are restrained. Along an edge rotationally restrained by *springs* the bending moment is proportional to the rotation of the edge $M_y = k\delta w / \delta y$, where k is the rotational spring constant. Along an edge rotationally restrained by a *stiffener* with torsional stiffness GI_t the restraining moment is ([15] p. 332) $M_y = GI_t \delta^3 w / \delta y^3$. In the Table the parameters of restraints, for the two cases, are defined as:

$$\zeta = \frac{D_{22}}{kL_y} \qquad \zeta' = \frac{D_{22}L_y}{GI_t} \qquad (1)$$

while the parameter ξ for a plate rotationally restrained by springs, and by a stiffener, are, respectively, as follows:

$$\xi = \frac{1}{1 + 10\zeta} \qquad \xi = \frac{1}{1 + 0.61(\zeta')^{1.2}} \qquad (2)$$

ANALYSIS OF LOCAL BUCKLING

First, each wall segment is considered to be simply supported (Fig. 2, a) and the critical $(N_{x,cr})^{ss}$ load for each wall segment is calculated [5]. The axial strain at which the wall segment buckles is calculated by $\varepsilon_x = (N_{x,cr})^{ss} a_{11}$, where a_{11} is the tensile compliance of the wall. (For a wall made of a single layer of orthotropic material $a_{11} = 1/(E_x h)$, where h is the thickness.) When the critical strains in the wall segments are identical, the segments buckle simultaneously under the load $(N_{x,cr})^{ss}$. When the critical strains are different the critical load is higher than $(N_{x,cr})^{ss}$. The segment with the lowest critical strain is considered further, because the wall segment (web or flange) in which the axial critical strain is the lowest is most susceptible to buckling. Then, we calculate the buckling load of this segment by treating it as a plate rotationally restrained by the adjoining wall segment or segments (Fig. 2b). The restraining effect depends on the configuration of the walls. We consider two cases:

1		$\frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} (2\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}))$	[12]
2		$\frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} (3.125\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2.33(D_{12} + 2D_{66}))$	[17]
3		$\frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} (4.53\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2.62(D_{12} + 2D_{66}))$	[12, 17]
4		$\frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} (2\sqrt{1 + 4.139\xi}\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + (2 + 0.62\xi^2)(D_{12} + 2D_{66}))$	[6, 9]
5		$\frac{12D_{66}}{L_y^2} + \frac{\pi^2 D_{11}}{L_x^2}$	[3]
6		$\frac{1}{L_y^2} (7\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 12D_{66})$	[7]
7		$\frac{1}{L_y^2} \left(\frac{7}{\sqrt{1 + 4.12\xi}} \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 12D_{66} \right)$	[7]
8		$\frac{1}{L_y^2} \left(\frac{3D_{22}}{\xi'} + 12D_{66} \right) \quad \text{when } 1.17\xi' \sqrt{\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}}} \geq 1$	[9]
		$\frac{1}{L_y^2} \left(\left(7 - 4.12\xi' \sqrt{\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}}} \right) \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 12D_{66} \right) \quad \text{when } 1.17\xi' \sqrt{\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}}} < 1$	
9		$\frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} (13.9\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 11.1(D_{12} + 2D_{66}))$	[12]

Table 1: Buckling load, $N_{x,cr}$ of unidirectionally loaded long plates. L_y is the width and L_x is the length of the plate ($L_x \gg L_y$). „ss” denotes a simply supported edge while “free” denotes a free edge.

Fig. 2: Modeling of local buckling of an axially loaded member

In the first case both edges of the restraining wall are attached to adjacent wall segments (this case is illustrated in Fig. 2). As a conservative estimate we assume that the deformed shape is cylindrical ([5], p. 339). For cylindrical bending the rotation of the edge, when moment M_y is applied along the edge is $\partial w / \partial y = M_y L_{rs} / (c(D_{22})_{rs})$, where the subscript rs refers to the restraining segment (Fig. 2b and 3a). The constant c depends on the edge conditions of the restraining wall (see Fig. 4). Consequently, the rotational spring constant is

$$k_o = \frac{c(D_{22})_{rs}}{L_{rs}} \quad (3)$$

For the case illustrated in Fig. 2 the two webs buckle simultaneously, and equal bending moments arise at both edges of the restraining wall. Consequently, as is shown in Fig. 4, $c=2$.

In the second case one of the axial edges of the restraining wall segment is free (Fig. 3b). In this case we estimate the restraining effect of this wall segment by considering its torsional stiffness [10]

$$GI_{to} = 4(D_{22})_{rs} L_{rs} \quad (4)$$

The above expressions are valid when no axial load is applied. The effect of axial loading is taken into account by an amplification factor r , defined as (see [15], pp. 15 and 424)

$$r = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{(N_x)_{rs}}{(N_{x,cr})_{rs}}} \quad (5)$$

where $(N_x)_{rs}$ is the applied axial load on the wall segment (Fig. 2b) and $(N_{x,cr})_{rs}$ is the buckling load of the simply supported restraining wall segment. r is unity when the axial load is zero and is infinity when the axial load is equal to the buckling load. By taking this amplification factor into account the spring constant and the restraining torsional stiffness become

$$k = \frac{c(D_{22})_{rs}}{L_{rs}} \frac{1}{r} \quad GI_t = 4(D_{22})_{rs} L_{rs} \frac{1}{r} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3: The restraining wall: (a) both edges are attached to adjacent walls; (b) one of the edges is free

Fig. 4: Deformed shape of a plate subjected to end moment M_y . ($M_y = 9cD_{22} / L_{rs}$)

The axial strains of the restraining and the buckled wall segments are the same, and, consequently, $(N_x)_{rs} = (N_{x,cr})_{bu} (a_{11})_{bu} / (a_{11})_{rs}$, where the subscript bu refers to the wall segment which buckles, $(N_{x,cr})_{bu}$ is the buckling load of the rotationally restrained buckled wall segment. The value of $(N_{x,cr})_{bu}$ is not known a priori. We may approximate $(N_{x,cr})_{bu}$ by the buckling load $(N_{x,cr})_{bu}^{ss}$ of a simply supported wall. With this approximation r becomes

$$r = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{(N_{x,cr})_{bu}^{ss} (a_{11})_{bu}}{(N_{x,cr})_{rs}^{ss} (a_{11})_{rs}}} \quad (7)$$

The above expressions can be directly applied for the buckling analysis of thin-walled box-, I-, C-, Z-, and L-members, subjected to axial load and bending. The appropriate expressions will be presented in the next section.

APPLICATION FOR BOX-, I-, L-, AND C-SECTIONS

We determined the local buckling loads of thin-walled beams by the derived expressions, and we compared the calculated loads to the results of finite element calculations, to the results of analytical solutions, and to experimental buckling loads. The analytical solution was developed by solving the equations given by Lee [11] numerically.

Box beam subjected to axial load – web buckling. First the local buckling loads are presented for a *box-beam* (Fig. 5a) subjected to axial compression, which was investigated by Qiao et al. [14]. The bending stiffnesses of both the flange and the web are $D_{11}=444$ Nm, $D_{22}=461$ Nm, $D_{12}=103$ Nm, $D_{66}=107$ Nm. The widths of the flange and the web are $b_f = 0.095$ 25 m and $b_w = 0.196$ 85 m.

With these values the buckling loads (considering the flange and the web as simply supported plates) are (Table 1, first row)

$$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-ss} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_f^2} (2\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})) = 1674 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (8)$$

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_w^2} (2\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})) = 392 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (9)$$

$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-ss} (a_{11})_f > (N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss} (a_{11})_w$ and, consequently, the web buckles first. (The web and the flange is made of the same material and have identical layups, hence $(a_{11})_f = (a_{11})_w$.) The web is restrained by the flanges. The spring constant is calculated by introducing $c=2$ (see Fig. 4) into Eqs.(6) and (7). It yields

Fig. 5: Cross-sections used in the numerical examples

Cross section	Figure	Load	$N_{x,cr}$ kN m	$N_{x,cr}^{FE}$ kN m	$N_{x,cr}^{AN}$ kN m	Error %
box	5a	axial	490	501	519	-5.6
box	5a	bending	1790	1960	-	-8.7
I	5b	axial	852	824 [14]	916	-6.9
I	5b	bending	1047	1100	-	-4.8
I	5c	axial	3257	2930	3187	2.2
I	5d	axial	580	622 [20]	627	-7.5
L	5e	axial	163	146	158	3.2
C	5f	axial	297	308	317	-6.3

Table 2: Results of the numerical examples. In calculating the Error, $N_{x,cr}$ was compared to the analytical buckling load ($N_{x,cr}^{AN}$) when available. When the sign of the error is negative, $N_{x,cr}$ is a conservative approximation of the buckling load

$$k = \frac{2D_{22}}{b_f} \left(1 - \frac{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w}{(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_f} \right) = 7414 \text{ N} \quad (10)$$

The parameter of restraint is (Eq. 1) $\zeta = D_{22}/k b_w = 0.316$, and consequently (Eq.2) $\xi = 1/(1+10 \zeta) = 0.240$. The buckling load of the web is (Table 1, fourth row)

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{rd-rd} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_w^2} \left(2\sqrt{1+4.139\xi} \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + (2+0.62\xi^2)(D_{12}+2D_{66}) \right) = 490 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (11)$$

This buckling load agrees closely with the result of the ANSYS finite element analysis (501 kN/m), and with the result of the analytical solution (519 kN/m).

Box beam subjected to bending – flange buckling. Next, the box-member considered above (Fig. 5a) is subjected to bending about the horizontal axis. The buckling loads (considering the flange and the web as simply supported plates) are as follows: $(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-ss}$ is given by Eq.(8), while $(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}$ by (Table 1, ninth row):

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_w^2} \left(13.9\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 11.1(D_{12}+2D_{66}) \right) = 2498 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (12)$$

$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_f < (N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w$ and, consequently, the flange buckles first ($(a_{11})_f = (a_{11})_w$). The flange is restrained by the webs. One end of the web is stabilized by the flange in tension, and hence we assume $c=4$ (see Fig. 4). The spring constant is calculated by Eqs.(6) and (7). It yields

$$k = \frac{4D_{22}}{b_f} \left(1 - \frac{(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_f}{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w} \right) = 3090 \text{ N} \quad (13)$$

The parameter of restraint is (Eq. 1) $\zeta = D_{22}/(k b_f) = 1.566$, and consequently (Eq.2) $\xi = 1/(1+10 \zeta) = 0.060$. The buckling load of the flange is (Table 1, fourth row):

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{rd-rd} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_f^2} \left(2\sqrt{1+4.139\xi} \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + (2+0.62\xi^2)(D_{12}+2D_{66}) \right) = 1790 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (14)$$

This result, together with the finite element solution, are given in Table 2.

I-beam subjected to axial load – flange buckling. We consider an I-section (Fig. 5b) subjected to axial compression ([16], [14]). The bending stiffnesses of both the flanges and the web are $D_{11}=698$ Nm, $D_{22}=326$ Nm, $D_{12}=127$ Nm, $D_{66}=103$ Nm. The widths of the flange and the web are $b_f = 0.102$ m and $b_w = 0.0956$ m.

When the flange is simply supported along one edge and free at the other edge, and the web is simply supported at both edges the buckling loads are (Table 1, fifth and first rows)

$$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free} = \frac{12D_{66}}{(b_f/2)^2} = 475 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (15)$$

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_w^2} \left(2\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2(D_{12}+2D_{66}) \right) = 1750 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (16)$$

$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f < (N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w$ and, consequently, the flange buckles first ($(a_{11})_f = (a_{11})_w$). The flange is restrained by the web. The spring constant is calculated by introducing $c=2$ (see Fig. 4) into Eqs.(6) and (7). However, the web, at each edge, restrains two (half) flanges, hence we must divide the spring constant by 2. It yields

$$k = \frac{1}{2} \frac{2D_{22}}{b_w} \left(1 - \frac{(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f}{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w} \right) = 2484 \text{ N} \quad (17)$$

The parameter of restraint is (Eq. 1) $\zeta = D_{22}/[k(b_f/2)] = 2.57$, and consequently (Eq.2) $\xi = 1/(1+10 \zeta) = 2.574$. The buckling load of the flange is (Table 1, seventh row):

$$(N_{x,cr})_f^{rd-free} = \frac{1}{(b_f/2)^2} \left(\frac{7\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}}}{\sqrt{1+4.12\xi}} + 12D_{66} \right) = 852 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (18)$$

This buckling load agrees closely with the result of the finite element analysis of Qiao et al. (824 kN/m), and with the result of the analytical solution (916 kN/m). The experimental buckling loads for the entire cross section [16] are 247 kN, 224 kN, and 222 kN, which yield 841 kN/m, 763 kN/m, and 759 kN/m.

I-beam subjected to bending – flange buckling. Next, the I-member considered above (Fig. 5b) is subjected to bending about the horizontal axis. The buckling loads (considering the flange and the web as simply supported plates) are as follows: $(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}$ is given by Eq.(15), while $(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}$ by (Table 1, ninth row):

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_w^2} \left(13.9\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 11.1(D_{12}+2D_{66}) \right) = 11152 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (19)$$

$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f < (N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w$ and, consequently, the flange buckles first ($(a_{11})_f = (a_{11})_w$). The flange is restrained by the webs. One end of the web is stabilized by the flange in tension, and hence we assume $c=4$ (see Fig. 4). The spring constant is calculated by Eqs.(6) and (7). It yields

$$k = \frac{1}{2} \frac{4D_{22}}{b_f} \left(1 - \frac{(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f}{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w} \right) = 6529 \text{ N} \quad (20)$$

The parameter of restraint is (Eq. 1) $\zeta = D_{22}/[k(b_f/2)] = 0.979$. The buckling load of the flange is (Table 1, seventh row):

$$(N_{x,cr})_f^{rd-free} = \frac{1}{(b_f/2)^2} \left(\frac{7\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}}}{\sqrt{1+4.12\zeta}} + 12D_{66} \right) = 1047 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (21)$$

I-beam subjected to axial load – web buckling. We now increase the thickness of the flanges of the I-beam three times (Fig. 5c, $h_f = 3 h_w$). In this case the bending stiffnesses of the web are $D_{11}=698$ Nm, $D_{22}=326$ Nm, $D_{12}=127$ Nm, $D_{66}=103$ Nm, while those of the flanges are 27 times higher. The beam is loaded by axial compression. The buckling load of the web, assuming simply supported edges $(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}$, is given by Eq.(16), while that of the flange is (Table 1, fifth row):

$$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free} = \frac{12(27D_{66})}{(b_f/2)^2} = 12830 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (22)$$

$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f > (N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w$ and, the web buckles first ($(a_{11})_w/(a_{11})_f = h_f/h_w = 3$). The torsional stiffness is calculated by Eqs.(6) and (7). It yields:

$$GI_t = 4D_{66}b_f \left(1 - \frac{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w}{(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f} \right) = 4D_{66}b_f \left(1 - \frac{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}h_f}{(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}h_w} \right) = 671 \text{ N} \quad (23)$$

The parameter of restraint is (Eq. 1) $\zeta' = D_{22}b_w/GI_t = 0.0465$, and consequently (Eq.2) $\xi = 1/(1+0.61\zeta'^{1.2}) = 0.985$. The buckling load of the web is (Table 1, fourth row)

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{rd-rd} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_w^2} \left(2\sqrt{1+4.139\xi}\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + (2+0.62\xi^2)(D_{12}+2D_{66}) \right) = 3257 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (24)$$

I-beam subjected to axial load – flange buckling. We also made a comparison with the results reported by Zureick, et al. [20] on the flange buckling of an Extren wide-flange vinylester beam. The cross section is shown in Fig. 5d, and the results are given in Table 2.

L-beam subjected to axial load. We consider an L-section (Fig. 5e) subjected to axial compression. The bending stiffnesses of both the flange and the web are $D_{11}=698$ Nm, $D_{22}=326$ Nm, $D_{12}=127$ Nm, $D_{66}=103$ Nm. The widths of the flange and the web are $b_f=0.051$ m and $b_w=0.102$ m.

When both the flange and the web are simply supported along one edge and free at the other edge, the buckling loads are (Table 1, fifth row)

$$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free} = \frac{12D_{66}}{b_f^2} = 475 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (25)$$

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-free} = \frac{12D_{66}}{b_w^2} = 119 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (26)$$

$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f > (N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-free}(a_{11})_w$ and, consequently, the web buckles first ($(a_{11})_f = (a_{11})_w$). The spring constant is calculated by Eqs.(6) and (7). It yields

$$GI_t = 4D_{66}b_f \left(1 - \frac{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-free}(a_{11})_w}{(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f} \right) = 15.8 \text{ N} \quad (27)$$

The parameter of restraint is (Eq. 1) $\zeta' = D_{22}b_w/GI_t = 2.11$, and, consequently, $1.17\zeta'\sqrt{D_{11}/D_{22}} = 3.09 > 1$. The buckling load of the web is (Table 1, eighth row)

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{rd-free} = \frac{1}{b_w^2} \left(\frac{3D_{22}}{\zeta'} + 12D_{66} \right) = 163 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}} \quad (28)$$

C-beam subjected to axial load – flange buckling. We consider a C-section (Fig. 5f) subjected to axial compression. The widths of the flange and the web are $b_f = 0.102 \text{ m}$ and $b_w = 0.102 \text{ m}$.

When the flange is simply supported along one edge and free at the other edge the buckling load $(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free} = 119$ is given by Eq.(26). When the web is simply supported at both edges the buckling load is (Table 1, first row)

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_w^2} \left(2\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right) = 1537 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (29)$$

$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f < (N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w$ and, consequently, the flange buckles first ($(a_{11})_f = (a_{11})_w$). The flange is restrained by the web. The spring constant is calculated by introducing $c=2$ (see Fig. 4) into Eqs.(6) and (7). It yields

$$k = \frac{2D_{22}}{b_w} \left(1 - \frac{(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss-free}(a_{11})_f}{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss-ss}(a_{11})_w} \right) = 5898 \text{ N} \quad (31)$$

The parameter of restraint is (Eq. 1) $\zeta = D_{22}/(k b_f) = 0.542$, and the buckling load of the flange is (Table 1, seventh row):

$$(N_{x,cr})_f^{rd-free} = \frac{1}{b_f^2} \left(\frac{7\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}}}{\sqrt{1 + 4.12\zeta}} + 12D_{66} \right) = 297 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \quad (32)$$

The results, together with the analytical and finite element solutions, are given in Table 2.

DISCUSSION

In this paper explicit expressions are developed for the local buckling analysis of FRP composite open and closed thin-walled beams and columns. In particular, simple formulas are presented for box-, I-, C-, Z-, and L-members subjected to axial load and bending. The presented results are compared to finite element calculations, to analytical analyses, and to experimental results.

In the derivation of the presented expressions several approximations were made: (i) Rather than considering an assembled section, we modeled the webs and flanges as individual orthotropic plates rotationally restrained at their edges. (ii) In calculating the restraining effect we assumed cylindrical bending. (iii) In the calculation of the amplification factor we used Eq.(7). (iv) For bending, we assumed $c=4$, i.e. the edge of the web at the flange in tension is built-in. (v) We calculated the buckling loads of plates with rotationally restrained edges by approximate expressions.

Note that some of the above approximations can be improved. For example, for the buckling loads of long plates (see v) more accurate (and more complicated) expressions are given in [10]. The effect of non cylindrical bending (see ii), (e.g. the effect of different buckling lengths of the individual elements) was investigated in [9]. In calculating the amplification factor (see iii) we may chose an iteration instead of the presented formula. These improvements may increase the accuracy of the calculation, however, the analysis becomes more complex, and less practical. Hence, we do not suggest any of these improvements.

We also compared [9] our results to the expressions available in the literature [5] for isotropic (steel) members, which were investigated extensively, and good agreement was found. On the basis of these comparisons, together with the results of finite element and analytical calculations, we may state that the presented expressions are reasonably accurate.

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